

DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL AIRSHIPS FOR INDOOR EXPLORATION AND INSPECTION OF THE CERN UNDERGROUND FACILITIES

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Abstract

In the past years, Windreiter collected vast experience in the construction and piloting of small indoor blimps, mostly applied to video capture and airship regattas. Within a recent cooperation with the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), the development of an autonomous indoor explorer airship was initiated. The experiments at CERN are characterized by an intense radiation field, thus human access is extremely restricted. This is problematic, as the state of running machinery is assessed offsite based on remote data coming from a number of static sensors and gauges installed inside experimental caverns. A potential solution would be an autonomous small airship equipped with cameras and other sensors that can enter radiation areas, avoiding the need for human intervention and thereby limiting health risks. Based on super lightweight balloons and newly developed electronics, a variety of small airships could be realized and deployed inside the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) detector caverns. A first prototype has already been successfully remotely piloted via video transmission inside the ALICE cavern. Enhancing this application, Windreiter is developing a blimp-specific indoor autopilot environment. Current available autopilots, often lack capabilities for indoor applications or cannot sense the blimp sluggish dynamics. Thus cameras, external reference systems and multiple sensors are implemented to enable stabilized flight and autonomous operation. This paper presents the current state of development of a new prototype version capable of achieving waypoint mission flights with over 2 hours of endurance, carrying scientific payloads, and featuring dimensions that allow operation in narrow environments. This work showcases various tests conducted on a waypoint-following mission, including results and performance measurements. Future project applications include deployments in upcoming CERN caverns, operating in strong magnetic fields and radiation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the deployment of robots in challenging and hazardous environments has significantly increased [1]. These advancements have proven beneficial across various industries, including nuclear decommissioning [2], offshore maintenance [3], space exploration [4], and deep mining [5]. Robots in these environments not only improve safety by minimizing human exposure to dangerous conditions but also enhance productivity in high-risk, unstructured facilities. In this context, the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) faces the challenge of designing robotic systems capable of operating in semi-structured and harsh environments, such as the underground caverns that house its particle detectors. CERN's primary facility,

the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), features four particle detectors—ATLAS, ALICE, CMS, and LHCb—each located in subterranean environments and characterized by strong magnetic and radiation fields during particle beam run. The maintenance, inspection, and upgrades of these detectors and their associated equipment are currently conducted by human personnel. However, as future detectors are expected to generate radiation levels that pose significant risks even when the particle beams are inactive [6], limiting human exposure is paramount. In certain areas, personnel may only be able to work for a few hours per year without exceeding safe radiation doses, which would severely hinder continuous maintenance operations and make complex, time-consuming tasks infeasible. To address these challenges, CERN's Experimental Physics (EP)

department has launched a research and development (R&D) program [7] which, as part of its strategic goal of developing technologies for future CERN experiments, has initiated the integration of robotic and automated systems into high-risk experimental cavern environments. These systems are designed to perform essential inspections and maintenance tasks without interrupting detector operations. Their capabilities include alarm verification and handling repetitive, time-consuming tasks such as continuous data acquisition. For cavern inspection and data collection, the strategy involves selecting both ground-based and aerial mobile platforms and equipping them with specialized payloads. In collaboration with Windreiter, an external partner, the group is developing a blimp specifically for CERN's cavern environments. These blimps are designed to autonomously navigate optimal paths, counteracting environmental disturbances, and will be fitted with advanced sensors for visual inspections, as well as tools for collecting spatial data on magnetic fields and radiation levels.

Windreiter is a small startup company that acts as an enabling technology keyplayer for lighter than air unmanned aerial vehicle niche. Operating from the headquarter in Grevenbroich, Germany, the company has realized various projects around airships of different sizes and capabilities. Well before the widespread emergence of copter drones, Windreiter airships enabled beautiful videography of the sensitive interior of churches. The open source airship project *silent_runner* has been built many times around the globe and eased the start into the lighter than air world for students and enthusiasts. With a unique envelope production facility, Windreiter delivers customized envelopes to airship builders worldwide and enabled uncounted blimp and rigid prototype constructions. Based on this experience, Windreiter was asked to take up the challenge given by the above CERN project. In a first quick and dirty attempt, a blimp was designed to demonstrate the overall feasibility and was flown remotely piloted via multiple live cameras through the complex industrial interior of the ALICE detector cavern inside the Large Hadron Collider. Based on this mobility test, the current blimp design was developed and is presented in this paper. It follows a number of predefined criteria which are the following: (1) Outer dimensions should not exceed a bounding box of 1.6 m x 0.6 m x 0.6 m. (2) All communication and video transmission must run via Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN), that is well established in the underground facility. (3) The blimp needs to carry and operate different sensors, such as a radiation monitoring device, a magnetic sensor or a high resolution camera. (4) The blimp manoeuvrability should allow

to navigate easy inside the narrow environment, yet motor forces and overall design must guarantee no harm to the sensitive scientific devices in the flight area, in any given blimp failure scenario. (5) Navigation and Guidance of the blimp should be autonomous, with supervision by an operator.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. General layout

The blimp will operate at very low speeds, thus no streamlined shape is required and a symmetric balloon was designed and produced from TRI-TAX foil. A total volume of 412 litres is estimated for this balloon. For the same reason, fins are omitted and flight stability is achieved by defining the center of gravity precisely below the center of buoyancy, as well as symmetric motor arrangement to apply thrust vectors to the airships mass center. Motors for forward/backward and heading control are positioned in a X-shape in order to remain inside the bounding box (see Figure 1). This position decreases the chance for the framed propellers to hit an obstacle as the soft envelope is the outermost element of the airship. Motors for altitude control are below the center of gravity in the main gondola of the blimp. All parts are fixed to a belt that is slung around the center of the balloon. This arrangement guarantees a spread of applied forces and allows easy replacement of the inner envelope.

Figure 1 depicts the general layout and the position of its fundamental components, that are described in the following section: (1) envelope, (2) left motors pair, (3) right motors pair, (4) belt, (5) vertical thrusters, (6) gondola with autopilot, battery and payload, (7) side view of the airship with dimensions.

Figure 1: General blimp layout.

2.2. Components

The airships components consist of the following elements:

- **Autopilot board** – A printed circuit board that was specifically designed for this purpose. It houses a microcontroller (Arduino 33 IOT) for wireless connectivity and processing of the autopilot firmware. A microSD slot for data logging is placed at the side of the PCB. Further, it provides battery power input and stabilization to 5V in order to power sensors and cameras. The board can control 4 DC motor channels directly and other actuators, motors or servos via PWM. Further a laser range meter used as an altimeter, IMU, barometer, air quality measure and magnetometer are implemented. This board is inspired by the Blimpduino project [8], but was designed with recent components from scratch including more functions yet arriving heavier at 22 g weight.
- **Motors** – Two pairs of coreless DC motors (7x16mm type), left and right, are run in parallel to allow forward/backward flight as well as turning. These 4 motors feature specifically designed and 3D printed propellers that are symmetric in their shape, thus providing symmetric thrust if driven forward or backward, see Figs. 2a and 2b. Normal propellers are efficient in one direction but inefficient in the opposing direction. The propellers designed here sacrifice some efficiency in order to allow better defined thrust in both directions which allows the blimp to perfectly turn on point or accurately mix forward flight and turning. Two downward pointing thrusters of the same type are run in parallel left and right of the gondola to provide lift. In this case standard asymmetric propellers are employed to overcome the blimp's moderate aerostatic heaviness. Indeed, the blimp mass and balance is realized in such a way that the blimp has a natural tendency to move downwards when no propulsive forces are applied, meaning that its weight exceeds the buoyancy force.
- **Battery** – A 1500 mAh 2S LiPo battery is employed for about 2 hours of continuous operation. This battery is placed below the center of buoyancy to allow replacement with a bigger battery if less operational payload range is required. The voltage of the battery is monitored by the autopilot.
- **Camera** – One downward facing wide angle lens camera is placed at the center of the gon-

dola to establish the video stream via WiFi that is later used for the indoor positioning system.

Figure 2: Specifically designed symmetric propeller.

2.3. Weights and Endurance

A number of blimp iterations resulted in a close to final design that is capable of achieving the desired performance and capabilities. As the most important figure of merit in blimp design is the weight to payload ratio, Tab. 1 displays the airships components and their weights. Based on this measurements, we achieve a payload of 180g that is computed as the difference between the estimated lift and the total weight of the blimp components. With the standard battery, whose weight has already been considered in the computation of the available payload, the blimp can reach 2 hours of non-stop flight operation. Of course, this is an optimistic estimate, as it does not account for the power consumption of the scientific payload. However, a portion of the payload can be devoted to a bigger battery (in principle, up to four times) to compensate for the extra power required.

Table 1: Blimp weight and payload.

Subsystem	Weight (g)	Number of Parts	Sum (g)
Motor	2.7	6	16.2
Propeller	1.2	6	7.2
X Motor Fins	2.5	4	10.0
Empty gondola	10.0	1	10.0
Autopilot	22.0	1	22.0
Camera	9.0	1	9.0
Battery 1500mAh	52.0	1	52.0
Envelope	93.8	1	93.8
Belt and wiring	25.0	1	25.0
Helium	73.6	1	73.6
Total			318.8
Estimated lift (g)			505.1
Payload (g)			186.3

2.4. Autopilot Firmware

The blimp's firmware consists of a complex architecture of procedures to perform the tasks of sensor

readout, position and attitude estimation, navigation, communication and data storage. In this section, we describe the development of the firmware module that ensures position hold. Being able to keep a stationary position is the base requirement for autonomous navigation but also simplifies a rover-mode where the operator gives relative movement commands rather than directly controlling the thrust of the motors. This firmware is written and compiled in the Arduino IDE and flashed directly on the CORTEX M0 processor of the Arduino board on which it is executed after startup. This ensures maximum reliability. The autopilot of the blimp requires an accurate estimation of the current position and velocity. To this end, the approach depicted in Fig. 3 is used. First, raw values are collected from all the available sensors. Then sensor-specific filters and conversions are applied to the raw values and the filtered sensor data are fused together according to their reliability to provide univocal information about velocity, that is used to update the position. This process is performed at 100 Hz, although each sensor has its own readout speed: 100 Hz for gyroscopes and accelerometers, 10 Hz for the laser-altimeter and the magnetometer and even lower or variable refresh rates for external sensors such as the positioning system.

Based on the previously calculated position and velocity, we derive the necessary actions that must be taken by the motors as shown in Fig. 4. Again, this follows a physical approach, where we first calculate the difference from the actual position to the desired position and the speed that is necessary to reach the desired position and attitude. This speed is compared to the current speed and based on the difference, the necessary acceleration or deceleration is calculated. Given a precise knowledge of the thrust of the motors, the blimp then tunes the motor thrust to the acceleration level that is needed. A mixing must be applied, as the forward facing motors are responsible for forward/backward thrust, as well as turning around the Z axis (yaw). The operator of the blimp can send control commands at any stage of this calculation process and either define the desired position (Rover Mode) or the desired velocity (Fly by Wire Mode) or directly control the motor thrust level (Manual Mode). In specific situations it might be useful to apply full direct control via manual mode, for example, if the blimp gets stuck and requires more motor power than that allowed by the Rover Mode authority, in order to dislodge the blimp from its stuck position. However, in normal operation, we expect the rover mode to be in charge of position hold and movement. The upcoming autopilot, would then consecutively pass waypoints to the rover mode for the blimp to follow a predefined

mission.

2.5. Indoor Positioning System

There are a variety of indoor positioning systems on the market that rely on different techniques and provide varying accuracies and update frequencies. Sonar acoustic, radar echo, laser or camera systems are available [9]. A market research revealed that the use of these systems is almost impossible in the complex and narrow cavern systems of the CERN facility as the costs would be enormous to reach sufficient coverage and accuracy. Thus, Windreiter decided to explore a solution, where reference tags printed on paper encode the current coordinate in the 3D space and are analysed by a camera on board of the blimp. So called ArUco tags [10], that encode their coordinate on the XY-plane, are printed, and are then spread inside the flying area according to their encoded coordinates, as shown in Fig. 5. As soon as the camera view picks up a tag, an algorithm estimates the blimp's absolute position and velocity, implementing the steps shown in Algorithm 1

Algorithm 1: Blimp Tracking and Analysis

Input: Camera view with ArUco tags
Output: Position and velocity of the blimp
while *camera view picks up a tag* **do**
 Read the ArUco Tag ID to retrieve the (X, Y, Z) coordinates;
 Measure the orientation of the tag relative to the camera to estimate the blimp's heading;
 Measure the distance between the camera and the tag in (X, Y, Z) to add this offset to the tag's position;
 Calculate the velocity of the blimp by comparing the current position with the previous position;
 Send the results to the blimp autopilot;
end

2.6. Test Mission

The performance of the blimp autopilot was assessed in a preliminary test mission featuring a sequence of three predefined waypoints, listed in Tab. 2. The blimp needs to reach the current waypoint and perform a specific action before moving to the following one. Currently, there is no path planner algorithm optimizing the order of the waypoints, but they are followed in the same order listed in Tab. 2. To keep into account the uncertainty of the position

Figure 3: Flowchart for sensor fusion and position estimates.

Figure 4: Flowchart for actuator control.

Figure 5: The blimp positioning system based on ArUco tags.

estimation from the current version of the indoor positioning system (Sec. 2.5), a box of influence of 1 m side is defined around each waypoint. This means that to accomplish a fly-through task (WP1 and 3), the center of mass of the blimp needs to pass inside the box. Similarly, a position-hold task (WP2) is accomplished if the center of mass of the blimp remains inside the box for the prescribed amount of time.

The flight test was performed in the Windreiter workshop environment including an ArUco Tag reference system and 4 external cameras to track the blimps position (Fig. 6). The flight data collected during the test mission were logged to on board SD card. The goal of this preliminary test was to assess the performance of the autopilot and to identify potential sources of uncertainty that can be improved in future release of the software. The following operations needs to be carried out to start the mission: (1) Switch on the blimp that boots and connects to the WiFi. (2) Once the control software is booted, it starts to stream the on board camera snapshots to a ground control station running the algorithm that is responsible for localizing the blimp

from the ArUco Tags. (3) The blimp is commanded to measure its own weight by gently increasing the thrust of the two downward pointing motors until it lifts-off. (4) The blimp is manually piloted to a position where the information coming from the external ArUco tags can be used to detect the blimps position in space. (5) The autopilot takes over and flies the predefined waypoint mission in an infinite loop.

Figure 6: Flight test area inside Windreiter workshop.

Table 2: Test mission waypoint data.

Waypoint	Task	X (m)	Y (m)	Z (m)	Bounds (m)
WP1	Fly-through	0	2	1.2	± 0.5
WP2	Position-hold (10 s)	0	-2	1.2	± 0.5
WP3	Fly-through	0	-2	2.2	± 0.5

2.7. Performance Metrics

The autopilot performance metrics used in this paper only consider the position error. However, also other parameters play a crucial role in the performance evaluation of an autopilot, such as waypoint overshoot.

To compute the position error, the time history of each waypoint task needs to be isolated by partitioning the mission time history and the following formulae need to be applied to each of these partitions. For fly-through tasks, the position error is computed as the minimum distance between the blimp center of mass position and the waypoint position:

$$(1) \quad e_{FT} = \min_k |\mathbf{P}(k) - \mathbf{P}_{WP_j}|$$

where $\mathbf{P}(k) = [x(k) \ y(k) \ z(k)]^T$ is the position vector measured at instant k and $\mathbf{P}_{WP_j} =$

$[x_{WP_j} \ y_{WP_j} \ z_{WP_j}]^T$ is the position vector of the j -th waypoint. For position-hold tasks, the position error is computed as the root mean squared difference between the blimp center of mass position and the waypoint position:

$$(2) \quad e_{PH} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N |\mathbf{P}(k) - \mathbf{P}_{WP}|^2}$$

3. RESULTS

This section presents the flight data collected during three different attempts of the waypoint mission introduced in Sec. 2.6. Fig. 7 shows the trajectory of the center of mass of the blimp during these attempts. The trajectory exhibits several jumps that are caused by the reset of the position and the velocity when a new ArUco tag is detected by the indoor positioning algorithm (Sec. 2.5). Efforts need to be devoted to improving this situation by increasing the accuracy of the indoor positioning system or by using a higher refresh rate to correct for the drift of the on-board navigation sensors. Moreover, the blimp does not seem to follow an optimal path between the waypoints, as several detours are taken from the direct path between the waypoints. This is clearly visible in the WP2 phase of the second attempt, shown in Fig. 7b.

Fig. 8 shows the evolution of the components of the position vector during the three attempts of the mission. The time history is partitioned in three phases, one for each waypoint, and the time instants in which each task is accomplished is shown with dashed lines for fly-through tasks and with a background pattern for position hold tasks. These data are used to assess the performance of the autopilot, that are summarized in Tab. 3 and 4.

Table 3: Position error computed at each waypoint across the three attempts.

Waypoint	Position Error (m)		
	Attempt 1	Attempt 2	Attempt 3
WP1	0.60 ^a	0.60 ^a	0.51 ^a
WP2	0.49 ^{b*}	0.41 ^{b*}	0.40 ^{b*}
WP3	0.69 ^a	0.72 ^a	0.72 ^a

^a Minimum distance (Eq. (1)).

^b Root mean square distance over position-hold time (Eq. (2)).

* Prescribed position-hold time (10 s) was not satisfied.

For fly-through tasks, the position error is always above 0.5 m in all the three attempts, because as soon as the tolerances on the position are satisfied (Tab. 2), the autopilot considers the task as accomplished and proceeds to the following waypoint.

(a) Attempt 1.

(b) Attempt 2.

(c) Attempt 3.

Figure 7: Blimp trajectory during the waypoint mission.

(a) Attempt 1.

(b) Attempt 2.

(c) Attempt 3.

Figure 8: Time history of the blimp position during the waypoint mission.

Table 4: Maximum consecutive hold time at WP2 across the three attempts.

Attempt	WP2 Hold Time (s)
1	3.13
2	5.86
3	8.38

For position-hold tasks, the position error is always below 0.5 m in all the three attempts, but this is due to the fact that the autopilot does not fulfill the prescribed position-hold time. Indeed, Tab. 4 shows that in all the three attempts the maximum consecutive hold time at WP2 is always below 10 s.

Fig. 8 shows the evolution of the blimp orientation during the three attempts of the mission. The time history is partitioned in three phases, one for each waypoint. Roll and pitch are taken directly from the gyroscope, thus being very noisy. They always exhibit limited oscillations as these are damped by the fact that the center of mass of the blimp is located below the center of buoyancy.

Fig. 10 shows a comparison between the blimp altitude above the ground coming from the ArUco positioning system and that measured by the laser-altimeter during the three attempts of the mission. The discrepancies between these two signals underline the importance of a good data fusion of different sources and trust estimates for data integrity, as the laser-altimeter seems to fail at a range of 1.6 m and yield wrong information during the first two attempts (Fig. 10a and 10b). However, also the ArUco readings requires further improvement, as it exhibits a jump every time a new ArUco tag is detected and the position and velocity reset accordingly. This can be improved, for instance, by applying camera calibration to correct for lens distortion if the identified tag is close to the edge of the camera projection plane. Furthermore, a better tuning of the altitude control is required to smooth the oscillations of several centimeters experienced during the phases that are supposed to be conducted at constant altitude.

4. DISCUSSION

This preliminary test successfully validated the autopilot's ability to complete an entire mission, providing valuable insights into the project's strengths and areas for improvement, confirming the promising direction of the project and its future goals.

Firstly, the autopilot effectively managed the sequence of planned operations, demonstrating its ability to autonomously perform waypoint navigation. Despite some imperfections in accuracy, the

autopilot successfully reached the predefined waypoints during the three attempts while maintaining adequate stability along the path, with the only exception of missing the task of staying within the WP2 box for at least 10 seconds on all three attempts (8.38 s was the maximum time reached during attempt three, as seen in Tab. 4).

Finally, Another positive outcome was the successful integration of sensors, which allowed for the collection of sufficient data to complete the mission without critical interruptions. Although some noise was present in the data, the system remained operational and did not experience major failures, indicating a certain level of robustness and reliability in the navigation framework as shown in Fig. 3.

Nonetheless, there is potential for further improvements. First, the raw data collected throughout the experiments presented significant noise, in all sensor readings, as evidenced in all the figures presented in Sec. 3. This requires a more robust filtering and fusion techniques to improve data accuracy and reliability. A key recommendation is to replace the current sensor fusion approach with a Kalman filter. This would enable a better estimation of the system's state by accounting for uncertainties and dynamically fusing data from multiple sensors.

Furthermore, the hold time condition, which ensures hovering capability at waypoints (in particular at WP 2), was never adequately met during the three attempts. This indicates a need for revisiting the control strategy or fine-tuning system parameters to achieve this condition for stable and reliable waypoint management.

Overshooting of waypoints, especially observed during the second attempt, further highlights the limitations in the system's precision. This issue might be mitigated by improving the control system's ability to react swiftly and more accurately to deviations.

Improving the autopilot precision is another critical area of improvement. The current tolerances and waypoint box size are too large (1 m³ bounding box volume), resulting in imprecise navigation. Reducing these tolerances and refining the algorithms governing autopilot functions would lead to more accurate control over the vehicle's movement.

Moreover, by analysing the trajectories flown between waypoints, it becomes evident that the path follows non-optimal logic, as the implementation of algorithms such as path planning and trajectory optimization is still lacking. Integrating these algorithms could significantly enhance the overall efficiency of the mission.

Lastly, the accuracy of the Indoor Positioning System (IPS) was found to be suboptimal. Specific issues, such as fisheye distortion on the camera lens,

Figure 9: Time history of the blimp orientation during the waypoint mission.

especially towards the periphery, contributed to the inaccuracies in localization. A more sophisticated calibration of the camera, or even using a blimp detection model as suggested in a CERN summer student report [11], could significantly enhance the positioning accuracy.

In conclusion, while the system shows promise, these identified areas for improvement highlight opportunities to enhance the robustness and precision of the system in future iterations.

5. CONCLUSION

In this manuscript, we presented the current status of an indoor inspection blimp to be used inside CERN detector caverns. The design features were highlighted, providing information about the general blimp layout and capabilities, as well as a description of the autopilot firmware. Preliminary test flights highlighted the strengths and weaknesses of the current version of the autopilot and provided insights on improvements for future releases, as well as inspiration to increase the accuracy of the indoor navigation system. Future work will focus on the development of a hybrid indoor positioning system, combining information coming from the ArUco tags

identified using the onboard camera and a deep learning blimp detection model using an external camera system. Efforts also need to be devoted towards the enhancement of the autopilot by integrating more sensors in the data fusion, adopting more advanced filtering techniques to sensor raw data, and fine tuning the autopilot parameters. The final development will require the integration of a scientific payload on-board, comprising, for instance, a magnetic sensor, a radiation camera, and/or a thermal camera, to ultimately become a tool that can be deployed for indoor inspection of harsh and cluttered environments.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Windreiter is industrial partner and contracted by CERN "DAI 10313522" to develop the given robotic blimp platform.

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